

SOME OBSERVATIONS ON AVIFAUNA DIVERSITY OF RTM NAGPUR UNIVERSITY CAMPUS, NAGPUR AND ITS VICINITY

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ABSTRACT

Attempts are made to record avifauna diversity of RTM Nagpur university campus, Nagpur and its vicinity. A total of 101 bird species were recorded belonging to 18 orders, 47 families and 84 genera. Passeriformes alone represent 43% (43) of the total birds recorded followed by Ciconiformes (8). Thirteen orders represents 2-7 birds. Podicipediformes, Upupiformes and Bucerotiformes consists one bird each. Among the families Columbidae represents maximum (7) number of birds followed by Accipitridae (6) and Ardeidae (6). In present observation River tern is the only bird belongs to near threatened category and 95 bird species are least concerned.

Key words: Avifauna, Birdchecklist, Nagpur, RTM Nagpur University

INTRODUCTION

I had an opportunity to stay in the vicinity of RTM (Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj) Nagpur University campus, Nagpur, Maharashtra State, India from 5th to 25th March 2014. Nagpur is situated between 20°30' to 21°45' N and 78°15' to 79°45' E around 312 m asl. The climate of Nagpur is almost dry throughout the year, temperature ranging from 10 to 47^o Celsius and receives annual rainfall around 1,205mm. RTM Nagpur university is one of the oldest Indian university spreads over around 318 acres of land with several plant species (Teak, Bamboo, Tamarand, Mango, Ficus, Jack fruit, Coconut, Several flowering plants) distributed in the campus garden with few grassland patches. Since, there are no published record on avifauna diversity of the said campus I have made an attempt to document the bird diversity. Survey was also conducted in Ambazhari Talaw and Garden, Vishveshwarayya National Institute of

Technology (VNIT) campus Nagpur and, in Ramtek (around 50 Km from Nagpur) during the above said period. Line transect and point transect methods are adopted to record the avifauna during the peak activity of birds from 7.00 to 10.30 AM in study area. Birds were photographed and observed by 10 x 50 X Olympus binocular and, identified using field guides by Kazmierczak (2000), Ali (2002) and Grimmett *et al.* (1998, 2011).

OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSION

During the above survey period a total of 101 bird species were documented (Table 1) belongs to 18 orders, 47 families and 84 genera. Columbidae family represents maximum (7) number of birds followed by Accipitridae (6) and Ardeidae (6); Cistcolidae consists 5 species; Sturnidae and Motacillidae consists 4 species each; Cuculidae, Strigidae, Hirundinidae, Muscicapinae and Picidae consists 3 species

each. Rest of the families represents two or one bird (Table 2). Among the orders Passeriformes represent maximum (43) number of birds followed by Ciconiiformes (8) and, Falconiformes and Columbiformes (7 bird species); Piciformes and Coraciiformes represent

5 birds each; Charadriiformes consist 4 birds; Cuculiformes and Strigiformes consist 3 birds each; Anseriformes, Apodiformes, Gruiformes, Psittaciformes, Pelicaniformes and Galliformes represents 2 birds each. The least (1) number of bird species represented by Podicipediformes,

Table 1. Showing avifauna recorded in RTM Nagpur University campus Nagpur and its vicinity

Sl. No.	Order/Family	Common Name	Scientific Name	Conservation status
1. Order GALLIFORMES				
1	1. Phasianidae	Indian Peafowl	<i>Pavo cristatus</i>	LC
2		Red Spurfowl	<i>Galloperdix spadicea</i>	LC
2. Order ANSERIFORMES				
3	2. Anatidae	Lesser whistling duck	<i>Dendrocygna javanica</i>	LC
4		Indian Spot-billed Duck	<i>Anas poecilorhyncha</i>	LC
3. Order PODICIPEDIFORMES				
5	3. Podicipedidae	Little Grebe	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	LC
4. Order CICONIIFORMES				
6	4. Ciconiidae	Woolly-necked Stork	<i>Ciconia episcopus</i>	LC
7		Asian Openbill	<i>Anastomus oscitans</i>	LC
8	5. Ardeidae	Indian Pond Heron	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	LC
9		Cattle Egret	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	LC
10		Intermediate Egret	<i>Mesophoyx intermedia</i>	LC
11		Great Egret	<i>Casmerodius albus</i>	LC
12		Little Egret	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	LC
13		Purple Heron	<i>Ardea purpurea</i>	LC
5. Order PELICANIFORMES				
14	6. Phalacrocoracidae	Little Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax niger</i>	LC
15		Great Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	LC
6. Order FALCONIFORMES				
16	7. Falconidae	Peregrine Falcon	<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	LC
17	8. Accipitridae	Brahminy Kite	<i>Haliastur indus</i>	LC
18		Black Kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	LC
19		Black-winged Kite	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	LC
20		Crested Serpent Eagle	<i>Spilornis cheela</i>	LC
21		Oriental Honey-buzzard	<i>Pernis ptilorhynchus</i>	LC
22		Shikra	<i>Accipiter badius</i>	LC
7. Order GRUIFORMES				
23	9. Rallidae	White-breasted Waterhen	<i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i>	LC
24		Eurasian Coot	<i>Fulica atra</i>	LC
8. Order CHARADRIIFORMES				
25	10. Charadriidae	Red-wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	LC
26		Little Ringed Plover	<i>Charadrius dubius</i>	LC
27	11. Scolopacidae	Common Sandpiper	<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i>	LC
28	12. Laridae	River Tern	<i>Sterna aurantia</i>	NT

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Sl. No.	Order/Family	Common Name	Scientific Name	Conservation status
9. Order COLUMBIFORMES				
29	13.Columbidae	Common Pigeon	<i>Columba livia</i>	LC
30		Laughing Dove	<i>Stigmatopelia senegalensis</i>	LC
31		Spotted Dove	<i>Stigmatopelia chinensis</i>	LC
32		Red Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia tranquebarica</i>	LC
33		Eurasian Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	LC
34		Oriental Turtle Dove	<i>Streptopelia orientalis</i>	LC
35		Yellow-footed Green Pigeon	<i>Treron phoenicopterus chlorigaster</i>	LC
10. Order PSITTACIFORMES				
36	14.Psittacidae	Rose-ringed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	LC
37		Plum-headed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula cyanocephala</i>	LC
11. Order CUCULIFORMES				
38	15.Cuculidae	Asian Koel	<i>Eudynamys scolopaceus</i>	LC
39		Southern Coucal	<i>Centropus parroti</i>	NA
40		Common Hawk Cuckoo	<i>Hierococcyx varius</i>	LC
12. Order STRIGIFORMES				
41	16.Strigidae	Brown Fish Owl	<i>Ketupa zeylonensis</i>	LC
42		Brown Wood Owl	<i>Strix leptogrammica</i>	LC
43		Spotted Owlet	<i>Athene brama</i>	LC
13. Order APODIFORMES				
44	17.Apodidae	Asian Palm Swift	<i>Cypsiurus balasiensis</i>	LC
45		Little Swift	<i>Apus affinis</i>	LC
14. Order UPUIFORMES				
46	18.Upupidae	Common Hoopoe	<i>Upupa epops</i>	LC
15. Order CORACIFORMES				
47	19.Coracidae	Indian Roller	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>	LC
48	20.Alcedinidae	Common Kingfisher	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	LC
49	21.Halcyonidae	White-throated Kingfisher	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	LC
50	22.Cerylidae	Pied Kingfisher	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	LC
51	23.Meropidae	Green Bee-eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	LC
16. Order BUCEROTIFORMES				
52	24.Bucerotidae	Indian Grey Hornbill	<i>Ocyrceros birostris</i>	LC
17. Order PICIFORMES				
53	25.Ramphastidae	Coppersmith Barbet	<i>Megalaima haemacephala</i>	LC
54		Brown-headed Barbet	<i>Megalaima zeylanica</i>	LC
55	26.Picidae	White-naped Woodpecker	<i>Chrysocolaptes festivus</i>	LC
56		Lesser Goldenback	<i>Dinopium benghalense benghalense</i>	LC
57		Speckled Piculet	<i>Picumnus innominatus</i>	LC
18. Order PASSERIFORMES				
58	27.Aegithinidae	Common Iora	<i>Aegithina tiphia</i>	LC
59	28.Campephagidae	Small Minivet	<i>Pericrocotus cinnamomeus</i>	LC
60		White bellied Minivet	<i>Pericrocotus erythropygus</i>	LC

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Sl. No.	Order/Family	Common Name	Scientific Name	Conservation status
61	29.Prionopidae	Common Woodshrike	<i>Tephrodornis pondicerianus</i>	LC
62		Long -tailed Shrike	<i>Lanius schach</i>	LC
63	30.Dicruridae	Black Drongo	<i>Dicrurus macrocercus</i>	LC
64		White-bellied Drongo	<i>Dicrurus caerulescens</i>	LC
65	31.Oriolidae	Indian Golden Oriole	<i>Oriolus kundoo</i>	NA
66	32.Rhipiduridae	White-browed Fantail	<i>Rhipidura aureola</i>	LC
67	33.Corvidae	House Crow	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	LC
68		Indian Jungle Crow	<i>Corvus culminatus</i>	NA
69	34.Paridae	Great Tit	<i>Parus major</i>	LC
70		Indian Yellow Tit	<i>Parus aplonotus</i>	NA
71	35.Hirundinidae	Dusky Crag Martin	<i>Ptyonoprogne concolor</i>	LC
72		Red-rumped Swallow	<i>Cecropis daurica</i>	LC
73		Wire-tailed Swallow	<i>Hirundo smithii</i>	LC
74	36.Pycnonotidae	Red-vented Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	LC
75	37.Cisticolidae	Ashy Prinia	<i>Prinia socialis</i>	LC
76		Grey-breasted Prinia	<i>Prinia hodgsonii hodgsonii</i>	LC
77		Plain Prinia	<i>Prinia inornata</i>	LC
78		Jungle Prinia	<i>Prinia sylvatica</i>	LC
79		Rufous-fronted Prinia	<i>Prinia buchanani</i>	LC
80	38.Sylviidae	Greenish Warbler	<i>Phylloscopus trochiloides</i>	LC
81		Common Tailorbird	<i>Orthotomus sutorius</i>	LC
82	39.Timaliidae	Tawny-bellied Babbler	<i>Dumetia hyperythra hyperythra</i>	LC
83		Jungle Babbler	<i>Turdoides striata orientalis</i>	LC
84	40.Zosteropidae	Oriental White-eye	<i>Zosterops palpebrosus</i>	LC
85	41.Sturnidae	Brahminy Starling	<i>Sturnia pagodarum</i>	LC
86		Asian Pied Starling	<i>Gracupica contra contra</i>	LC
87		Common Myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	LC
88		Rosy Starling	<i>Pastor roseus</i>	NA
89	43.Muscicapinae	Oriental Magpie Robin	<i>Copsychus saularis</i>	LC
90		Indian Robin	<i>Saxicoloides fulicatus</i>	LC
91		Pied Bushchat	<i>Saxicola caprata</i>	LC
92	44.Dicaeidae	Thick-billed Flowerpecker	<i>Dicaeum agile</i>	LC
93		Pale-billed Flowerpecker	<i>Dicaeum erythrohynchos</i>	LC
94	45.Nectariniidae	Purple-rumped Sunbird	<i>Leptocoma zeylonica</i>	LC
95		Purple Sunbird	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	LC
96	46.Passeridae	House Sparrow	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	LC
97	47.Estrildidae	Scaly-breasted Munia	<i>Lonchura punctulata</i>	LC
98	48.Motacillidae	Grey Wagtail	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	LC
99		White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	LC
100		White-browed Wagtail	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	LC
101		Paddyfield Pipit	<i>Anthus rufulus</i>	LC

Note: Conservation Status: IUCN 2014 - NT: Near Threatened, LC: Least concerned
- NA – IUCN assessment is not available

Upupiformes, Psittaciformes and Bucerotiformes (Fig. 1).

River Tern *Sterna aurantia* is the only bird belongs to Near threatened category in present observation. IUCN assessment for conservation status is not available for Southern Coucal *Centropus parroti*, Indian Golden Oriole *Oriolus kundoo*, Indian Jungle Crow *Corvus culminatus*,

Indian Yellow Tit *Parus aplonotus*, and Rosy Starling *Pastor roseus*. Rest of the birds is least concerned (IUCN 2014, BirdLife International 2014, Fig. 2). Passeriformes dominating the study area may be it is due to the study area consisting large number of flowering plants and fruiting trees supporting frugivorous and insectivorous birds. In present observation we tried to identify the subspecies of Lesser

Figure 1. Showing order wise number of birds recorded in RTM Nagpur University, Nagpur and its vicinity

Figure 2. Showing conservation status of birds recorded in RTM Nagpur University, Nagpur and its vicinity

Goldenback, Grey-breasted Prinia, Tawny-bellied Babbler, Jungle Babbler and Asian Pied Starling (Table 1).

Table-2. Showing family wise number of birds recorded in RTM Nagpur university campus, Nagpur and its vicinity.

Sl. No.	Name of the Family	Number of birds recorded
1	Podicipedidae	1
2	Falconidae	1
3	Scolopacidae	1
4	Laridae	1
5	Upupidae	1
6	Coracidae	1
7	Alcedinidae	1
8	Halcyonidae	1
9	Cerylidae	1
10	Meropidae	1
11	Bucerotidae	1
12	Aegithinidae	1
13	Oriolidae	1
14	Pycnonotidae	1
15	Passeridae	1
16	Estrildidae	1
17	Zosteropidae	1
18	Rhipiduridae	1
19	Phasianidae	2
20	Anatidae	2
21	Ciconiidae	2
22	Phalacrocoracidae	2
23	Rallidae	2
24	Charadriidae	2
25	Psittacidae	2
26	Apodidae	2
27	Dicaeidae	2
28	Nectariniidae	2
29	Ramphastidae	2
30	Campephagidae	2
31	Dicruridae	2
32	Corvidae	2
33	Paridae	2
34	Sylviidae	2
35	Timaliidae	2
36	Prionopidae	2
37	Cuculidae	3
38	Strigidae	3
39	Hirundinidae	3
40	Muscicapinae	3

41	Picidae	3
42	Sturnidae	4
43	Motacillidae	4
44	Cistcolidae	5
45	Ardeidae	6
46	Accipitridae	6
47	Columbidae	7
Total		101

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